

Building new tools for data sharing and re-use through a transnational investigation of the socio-economic impacts of protected areas (PARSEC).

Alison Specht

University of Queensland, the Australian Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN).

BELMONT FORUM

PARSEC is a project sponsored by the Belmont Forum as part of its Collaborative Research Action (CRA) on **Science-Driven e-Infrastructures Innovation (SEI)**, with funding from FAPESP, the ANR, JST and the NSF, with collaborators from Australia, and support from the synthesis centre CESAB of the French Foundation for Research on Biodiversity.

CESAB
CENTRE FOR THE SYNTHESIS AND ANALYSIS
OF BIODIVERSITY

AGENCE NATIONALE DE LA RECHERCHE
ANR

FAPESP
FUNDAÇÃO DE AMPARO À PESQUISA
DO ESTADO DE SÃO PAULO

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We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the land and sea in all nations. We honour their profound connections to land, water, biodiversity and culture and pay our respects to their Elders past, present and emerging.

*The **Belmont Forum** is a partnership of funding organisations, international science councils, and regional consortia committed to the advancement of global environmental science. It aims to accelerate the delivery of data-driven environmental research to remove critical barriers to sustainability by aligning and mobilizing international resources.*

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*The **Belmont Forum Science-Driven e-Infrastructures Innovation (SEI) CRA** intimately links research thinking and technological innovation toward accelerating the full-path of discovery-driven data use and open science. The objective is to enable a broader [than currently engaged] scientific community to benefit from identified new and potentially disruptive demonstrators or pilots toward solutions.*

The SEI projects were selected on the basis that they were

- *science-driven,*
- *transnational and collaborative,*
- *inter-disciplinary and/or trans-disciplinary, and*
- *problem solving and translatable.*

They were to be well-positioned to address one or more of the methodological, technological and/or procedural challenges currently facing interdisciplinary and trans-disciplinary environmental change research working with multi-source transnational data.

An evolving awareness of the need for global collaboration in environmental science research

Data organisation. A cacophony of responses, 1

- 2011** Investigators are expected to share with other researchers, at no more than incremental cost and within a reasonable time, the primary data, samples, physical collections and other supporting materials created or gathered in the course of the work under NSF grants.
- 2014** Since February 2014, the ARC has required researchers to outline how they plan to manage research data arising from ARC-funded research. From 2020, this requirement forms part of the agreement for funding under the National Competitive Grants Program.
- 2019** In line with its Open Science policy, the French National Research Agency (ANR) requires all projects funded in 2019 onwards to produce a Data Management Plan (DMP) setting out how research data will be produced, reused, stored, protected, disseminated and, where applicable, retained for a significant period of time.

Data organisation. A cacophony of responses, 2

Box 2 | The FAIR Guiding Principles

To be Findable:

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

To be Accessible:

- A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

To be Interoperable:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

To be Reusable:

- R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Carroll, S.R., et al. 2021. Operationalizing the CARE and FAIR Principles for Indigenous data futures. *Sci Data* 8, 108. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-00892-0>

Lin, D., et al. 2020. The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Scientific Data* 7, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

Wilkinson, M.D., et al. 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

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Box 1 The TRUST Principles

Principle	Guidance for repositories
Transparency	To be transparent about specific repository services and data holdings that are verifiable by publicly accessible evidence.
Responsibility	To be responsible for ensuring the authenticity and integrity of data holdings and for the reliability and persistence of its service.
User Focus	To ensure that the data management norms and expectations of target user communities are met.
Sustainability	To sustain services and preserve data holdings for the long-term.
Technology	To provide infrastructure and capabilities to support secure, persistent, and reliable services.

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- A2. metadata are accessible, even when not the data themselves

To be Interoperable:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and extensible language, vocabulary, and ontology that can be processed by a computer and accepted by peers and communities
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other data

To be Reusable:

- R1. (meta)data are richly described with machine-actionable information
- R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data license and provenance
- R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
- R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant standards

Box 1 The TRUST Principles

Principle	Guidance for repositories
Transparency	To be transparent about specific repository services and data holdings that are verifiable by publicly accessible evidence.
Accountability	To be responsible for ensuring the authenticity and integrity of data holdings and for the reliability and persistence of its service.
Responsibility	To ensure that the data management norms and expectations of target user communities are met.
Sustainability	To sustain services and preserve data holdings for the long-term.
Security	To provide infrastructure and capabilities to support secure, persistent, and reliable services.

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Building new tools for data sharing and re-use through a transnational investigation of the socio-economic impacts of protected areas (PARSEC).

PARSEC : Building New Tools for Data Sharing and Reuse through a Transnational Investigation of the Socioeconomic Impacts of Protected Areas

Consortium Leaders: Nicolas Mouquet, David Mouillot, Alison Specht and Shelley Stall.

<http://parsecproject.org>

Objectives

(a) Predict the socioeconomic outcomes of natural protected areas (PAs) on rural communities using a novel combination of satellite imagery and artificial intelligence;

(b) Determine the influence of PAs on consumption expenditure and asset health of rural communities;

(c) Improve future environmental decision-making;

(d) Improve digital connections between researchers, their funding, publications and data;

(e) Improve recommendations for the research data workflow and skills for research teams;

(f) Increase the number of citations to data sets and better attribute them to the data creator;

(g) Promote credit for open and FAIR data management and preservation for data reuse;

(h) Provide tools for researchers to view how the data they have deposited is used and cited.

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FUNDING: 1258K€

Duration: 48 months

Participating countries

BRAZIL: University of São Paulo - FAPESP (P. Pizzigatti Corrêa) plus postdoc and technical support (FAPESP)

FRANCE: Foundation for Research on Biodiversity, University of Toulouse III - ANR (N. Mouquet)

JAPAN: National Institute of Information & Communications Technology, Research Institute for Humanity and Nature - JST (Y. Murayama)

USA: American Geophysical Union - NSF (S. Stall)

Cooperating partners

NCI, Australia (L. Wyborn), BGS, UK (H. Glaves)

Associated organisations

DataCite, ORCID, ESIP, RDA, EDI, WDS, AST, JWP, TNC

Building new tools for data sharing and re-use through a transnational investigation of the socio-economic impacts of protected areas (PARSEC).

Unique components:

- 1. To conduct interdisciplinary, transnational synthesis science (**The Synthesis Strand (A)**) while*
- 2. testing novel approaches to the management and preservation of environmental and socio-economic data (**The Data Science Strand (B)**)*

Aim of this combination

These two strands will learn from each other, with 'domain' scientists better equipped to practice good data management, and data scientists better able to 'speak with' and respond to researcher priorities.

A. The science question: do Protected Areas help or hinder local communities?

- Benefits: well-being
- Neutral outcomes: food security
- Negative effects

ANALYSIS

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0306-2>

nature
sustainability

Well-being outcomes of marine protected areas

Natalie C. Ban^{1*}, Georgina Grace Gurney², Nadine A. Marshall³, Charlotte K. Whitney¹, Morena Mills⁴, Stefan Gelcich⁵, Nathan J. Bennett^{6,7,8}, Mairi C. Meehan⁹, Caroline Butler¹⁰, Stephen Ban¹¹, Tanya C. Tran¹, Michael E. Cox¹² and Sara Jo Breslow¹³

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Assessing the Effect of Marine Reserves on Household Food Security in Kenyan Coral Reef Fishing Communities

Emily S. Darling^{1,2,a*}

1. Earth to Ocean Research Group, Simon Fraser University, Burnaby, BC, Canada; 2. Society, Mombasa, Kenya

Science of the Total Environment 763 (2021) 144399

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Science of the Total Environment

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/scitotenv

Are protected areas good for the human species? Effects of protected areas on rural depopulation in Spain

D. Rodríguez-Rodríguez^{a,b,*}, R. Larrubia^a, J.D. Sinoga^a

Accelerated Human Population Growth at Protected Area Edges

George Wittemyer,[†] Paul Eisen, William T. Bean, A. Coleman O. Burton, Justin S. Brashares^{*,†}

Protected areas (PAs) have long been criticized as creations of and for an elite few, where associated costs, but few benefits, are borne by marginalized rural communities. Contrary to predictions of this argument, we found that average human population growth rates on the borders of 306 PAs in 45 countries in Africa and Latin America were nearly double average rural growth, suggesting that PAs attract, rather than repel, human settlement. Higher population growth on PA edges is evident across ecoregions, countries, and continents and is correlated positively with international donor investment in national conservation programs and an index of park-related funding. These findings provide insight on the value of PAs for local people, but also highlight a looming threat to PA effectiveness and biodiversity conservation.

www.sciencemag.org SCIENCE VOL 321 4 JULY 2008

B. The data science question: How can the researcher/domain expert benefit from new data science innovation and embed it in their practice

- Through providing exemplars?
- Provide educational packages?
- Create rewards for data sharing and re-use?
- A combination of the above? or other...

A distributed exercise

The synthesis strand

Selection of
protected areas
(PA), adjacent
settlements and
mirror sites

Model the socio-
economic
outcomes of the
effects of creation
of PAs on those
settlements using
remote sensing
and AI

Inspired by: Jean et al. 2016. *Science* 353, 790–794. doi: 10.1126/science.aaf7894
Yeh et al. 2020. *Nat Communications* 11, 2583. doi: 10.1038/s41467-020-16185-w *et al.*

Data requirements

- Time series data
- Documentation of protected areas across the world
 - Source: World Database for Protected Areas – collected from each country and aggregated in the UK. Ideally this would present a good comparison between countries.
- Remote sensing
 - Various sources. Around villages/townships proximal to a PA, before and after its creation, and similar for reference sites remote from a PA.
- Socio-economic data
 - Source: household (census) data in each country (sometimes integrated through Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS))

Repositories...
FAIR Data...
Preservation...
Rich Metadata...
OK? Got it?

Data Science Strand Team Members

Data strand

Stall, Shelley. (2021, June). PARSEC: A FAIR Data Use Case with 40 Researchers, 6 Countries, and one Data Management Plan. Presented at the Sustainability Research & Innovation Congress 2021 (SRI2021), Brisbane, Australia: Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4978466>

Repositories...
FAIR Data...
Preservation...
Rich Metadata...
OK? Got it?

**Data Science
Strand Team Members**

Data strand

Um...
Not Sure What You
Mean.

**Synthesis Science
Strand Team Members**

Stall, Shelley. (2021, June). PARSEC: A FAIR Data Use Case with 40 Researchers, 6 Countries, and one Data Management Plan. Presented at the Sustainability Research & Innovation Congress 2021 (SRI2021), Brisbane, Australia: Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4978466>

Implementation of support for a research project guided by the Belmont DDOMP*

*Bishop et al. 2020. Data Curation Profiling to Assess Data Management Training Needs and Practices to Inform a Toolkit. Data Science Journal 19, 4. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-004>

Stall et al. 2021. PARSEC DDOMP Workbook Checklist. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4909852>

Stall et al. 2021. PARSEC Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4910115>

Building new tools for data sharing and re-use through a transnational investigation of the socio-economic impacts of protected areas (PARSEC).

Challenges

- Collaboration
 - Languages, time zones, disciplinary approach, availability of expertise
 - Lag in development of common goal, relationships and trust due to covid19
- Data availability
 - Global sources not fit for purpose, e.g. WDPA has many translation errors (year of creation, IUCN category, etc)
 - PA classifications and nomenclature varies between countries
 - DHS / HDI data are not systematic in time or across countries. -> need to find alternatives
- Analysis
 - Difficulty with comparative baselines in each country
 - Correlation, not causality

Outputs

II Simpósio do Centro de Saúde Global (CSG) UNIFESP

Interação Saúde e Meio Ambiente

29 de junho de 2021
9:00 - 17:00 h

Inscrições: SIEIX
<https://sistemas.unifesp.br/jaca/di/proce-sieix/index.php?page=INS&acao=2&code=20136>

Transmissão: Youtube
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ve5FogRaBds>

UNIFESP
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CENTRO DE SAÚDE GLOBAL

agits
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Agência de Inovação Tecnológica e Social

SRI 2021

Sustainability of biodiversity conservation: too expensive for humans or can we find solutions?

June 13, 7:00 pm Brisbane time
June 13, 5:00 am New York / 10:00 am London

#SRI2021

PRACTICE PAPER

FAIRness Literacy: The Achilles' Heel of Applying FAIR Principles

Romain David^{1,2}, Laurence Mabile³, Alison Specht⁴, Sarah Stryeck⁵, Mogens Thomsen³, Mohamed Yahia⁶, Clement Jonquet⁷, Laurent Dollé⁸, Daniel Jacob⁹, Daniele Bailo¹⁰, Elena Bravo¹¹, Sophie Gachet¹², Hannah

David, R, et al. 2020. FAIRness Literacy: The Achilles' Heel of Applying FAIR Principles. *Data Science Journal*, 19: 32, pp.1-11. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-032>

- code
- conference posters, presentations and sessions
- guidelines and catalogues
- papers and preprints
- theses
- training, workshops, round tables

PARSEC

A Deep-Learning Method for the Prediction of Socio-Economic Indicators from Street-View Imagery Using a Case Study from Brazil

RESEARCH PAPER

JEANETH MACHICAO ● SHELLELY STALL ●
ALISON SPECHT ● KATIA FERRAZ ●
DANTON VELLENIKH ● LAURENCE MABILE ●
LEANDRO MENEGUZZI ● MARGARET O'BRIEN ●
ROMAIN DAVID ● PEDRO CORRÊA ●

*Author affiliations can be found in the back matter of this article

u[ubiquity press

Repository Guidelines

Types of Repository

Most repositories fall into one of two main categories: domain or generalist. Most of what follows on repository selection focusses more heavily on domain repositories, since they are more specialist, and thus more likely to fulfil both the common functions you would want from a repository, as well as any specific needs you may have within your research field(s).

Domain Repositories

A domain repository—sometimes known as a ‘subject-based’ repository—will specialize in a specific research field or data type. It usually has a well-defined group of users at which its data and services are aimed, its ‘Designated Community’. In many cases, domain repositories have a national or regional remit, or at least are publicly funded, and thus you will be able to deposit your data (and access others data) free of charge. They may also be part of a wider network of similar national repositories or be subject to international agreements regarding data sharing and management, which can ensure a wider pool of expertise and guarantees that multiple mirrored copies of your data exist.

Generalist Repositories

A generalist repository is a generic, multi-subject repository. Typical examples include institutional repositories serving research performing organizations such as a university library, open access repositories such as Zenodo or Dryad, and technical service providers such as Figshare. The user community of a generalist repository will be very broad and may even be the general public at large. Because of this, and since you may be a (paying) ‘client’ generalist repositories will often rely on data depositors to manage their own data. Many do not offer services beyond simple archiving—static, long-term preservation—although an institutional repository (or a paid service contract) may include curation expertise to help with (for instance) basic metadata.

Benefits of Storing Research Data in a Repository

There are many advantages to you as both a data producer and data user if you and your peers choose to preserve data in a repository. Of course, not all repositories are created equal, and these potential benefits are only realized by selecting a repository that does its job correctly, as described in the next section.

If you are a...

Data Producer/Depositor	Data User
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Your Data Management Plan is fulfilled (i.e., satisfies funders/Open Data requirements). ✓ The initial investment of collecting your data is preserved. ✓ You have the satisfaction that your data are being stewarded correctly and remain useful and meaningful. ✓ Your data are looked after long term, even if the data service discontinues. ✓ The ease of discovery of your data is increased. ✓ Publication, reuse or repurposing, and citation¹ is facilitated for your data. ✓ Recognized expertise is available to assist you with technicalities. ✓ It can be ensured that any necessary/wanted conditions on access and use, as well as licensing, are adhered to. (N.B. This is especially important for sensitive data.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ You can easily discover data. ✓ You can easily understand your access and usage rights ✓ You can reuse/repurpose data without the costs of collection/production. ✓ You can verify (and thus build on) others results, accelerating scientific knowledge. ✓ You can cite peers, knowing that the data will still exist into the future. ✓ You have the satisfaction that the data are original/uncompromised, and that any changes are recorded (provenance). ✓ (Re)Use of the data is made easier through full/appropriate metadata in an international or community standard. ✓ Ability to give feedback to the data producer/holder.

The PARSEC Data Strand has been actively creating guidelines, toolkits and a series of seminars and workshops to help users across all aspects of the research data lifecycle, including vocabularies

MANAGE YOUR DIGITAL OBJECTS – RESEARCH TEAM MEMBER CHECKLIST

Establishing common team resources and a schedule for digital object management during a project will ease the burden of documentation and preservation – streamlining your publications.

- ESTABLISH AND USE A COMMON SET OF TEAM RESOURCES.**
- Before or near the start of the project, make decisions on what resources the team will use to:
 - Communicate and disseminate information. e.g., Slack channel, email
 - Develop and manage documents during the project. e.g., Google Drive
 - Store datasets during the project, considering size and access/controls. e.g., OSF, <https://osf.io>, an institutional repository

DIGITAL PRESENCE CHECKLIST

Connect your research to your data, software, institution, and more. Use this checklist to optimize your digital presence, increase discovery of your work to potential collaborators and partners, and receive credit when others use your work.

- YOU. YOUR ORCID.**
- Enable your own ORCID.** It provides a persistent digital identifier that distinguishes you from other researchers and supports automated linkages between you and your research activities. Go here to register: <https://orcid.org>, and select “For Researchers”.
 - Include your ORCID on all scholarly work.** This includes your publications, datasets, software, presentations, posters, signature block of your emails. Everything. This helps with linking to your ORCID profile.
 - Keep your ORCID profile current.**
 - Enable automatic updates from Crossref and DataCite. [AGU Digital Presence blog post](#) has the detailed steps.
 - Set a reminder every three months to ensure all your work is connected and current in your ORCID profile. Make sure your current affiliation and email are included and public for viewing. Add a second email (which can be private) to ensure account access should one become locked.

- YOUR PUBLICATIONS. THE DIGITAL OBJECT IDENTIFIER (DOI) + YOUR ORCID.**
- Include your ORCID as well as your co-authors ORCID on your publications.**
 - When given a choice, use journals that require your ORCID as well as your co-authors. In this way your paper will be registered along with your ORCID and automatically linked.
 - If your selected journal does not require ORCIDs, include it anyway. Place your ORCID as close to your name as possible. Also include the ORCIDs of your co-authors.

- YOUR DATASETS. DOIS / PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS (PIDs) + YOUR ORCID.**
- Select a repository that supports discovery and preferably is specific to your data type** (e.g., Domain /Discipline Repository).

<https://zenodo.org/communities/parsec/?page=1&size=20>

454 Works

Publication Year

<input type="checkbox"/>	2022	22
<input type="checkbox"/>	2021	63
<input type="checkbox"/>	2020	30
<input type="checkbox"/>	2019	51
<input type="checkbox"/>	2018	32
<input type="checkbox"/>	2017	26
<input type="checkbox"/>	2016	93
<input type="checkbox"/>	2015	12
<input type="checkbox"/>	2014	7
<input type="checkbox"/>	2013	19
<input type="checkbox"/>	2012	16
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Work Type

<input type="checkbox"/>	Text	199
<input type="checkbox"/>	Dataset	109
<input type="checkbox"/>	Journal Article	96
<input type="checkbox"/>	Collection	41

Data from: Phylogenetic signal in module composition and species connectivity in compartmentalized host-parasite networks

Boris R. Krasnov, Miguel A. Fortuna, David Mouillot, Irina S. Khokhlova, Georgy I. Shenbrot & Robert Poulin
Version 1 of Dataset published 2011 in [DRYAD](#)

Across different taxa, networks of mutualistic or antagonistic interactions show consistent architecture. Most networks are modular, with modules being distinct species subsets connected mainly with each other and having few connections to other modules. We investigate the phylogenetic relatedness of species within modules and whether a phylogenetic signal is detectable in the within- and among module connectivity of species using 27 mammal-flea networks from the Palaearctic. In the 24 networks that were modular, closely-related hosts co-occurred in the same module more often than expected by chance; in contrast, this was rarely the case for parasites. The within- and among-module connectivity of the same host or parasite species varied geographically. However, among-module but not within-module connectivity of host and parasites was somewhat phylogenetically constrained. These findings suggest that the establishment of host-parasite networks results from the interplay between phylogenetic influences acting mostly on hosts and local factors acting on parasites, to create an asymmetrically constrained pattern of geographic variation in modular structure. Modularity in host-parasite networks seems to result from the shared evolutionary history of hosts and by trait convergence among unrelated parasites. This suggests profound differences between hosts and parasites in the establishment and functioning of bipartite antagonistic networks.

DOI registered November 29, 2011 via DataCite.

👤 1 Citation 👁 139 Views 📄 39 Downloads

Dataset

English

Desired outcome:

not only a good scientific product but also a workflow and product that is transparent, open, and reproducible

PARSEC : Building New Tools for Data Sharing and Reuse through a Transnational Investigation of the Socioeconomic Impacts of Protected Areas

Consortium Leaders: Nicolas Mouquet, David Mouillot, Alison Specht and Shelley Stall.

<http://parsecproject.org>

Objectives

- (a) Predict the socioeconomic outcomes of natural protected areas (PAs) on rural communities using a novel combination of satellite imagery and artificial intelligence;
- (b) Determine the influence of PAs on consumption expenditure and asset health of rural communities;

- (c) Improve future environmental decision-making;
- (d) Improve digital connections between researchers, their funding, publications and data;
- (e) Improve recommendations for the research data workflow and skills for research teams;

- (f) Increase the number of citations to data sets and better attribute them to the data creator;
- (g) Promote credit for open and FAIR data management and preservation for data reuse;
- (h) Provide tools for researchers to view how the data they have deposited is used and cited.

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